

THE EXTENT TO WHICH THE RESEARCH OUTPUTS OF THE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION DEVELOPMENT CENTER AT SANA'A UNIVERSITY CONTRIBUTE TO ADMINISTRATIVE DEVELOPMENT

**Abdul Razzaq Abdullah Al-Mahbashi ¹, Ali Abdullah Al-Awadi ²,
Ahmed Mohamed Nasser ³ and Fuad Mansoor Al-Ward ⁴**

^{1,2,3}Public Administration Development Center, Sana'a University, Sana'a, Yemen.

⁴Translation, English Language, Sana'a University, Sana'a, Yemen.

Email: ¹almhbshybdalrzaq1@gmail.com, ²Aalawadi660@gmil.com,

⁴alwardd1982@gmail.com/ f.alward@su.edu.ye, ⁴ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1946-4123>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11076849](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11076849)

Abstract

The research aims to identify the extent to which the research outputs of the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University contribute to the administrative development of government and private institutions in the Republic of Yemen. To achieve the goal of the research, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The research community and its sample consisted of (225) scientific theses, representing the scientific productivity of the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University. After analyzing the data, the research reached some results, the most important of which are: 1) Most of the theses were from the achievement of male students with (205) theses, at a rate of (91%), and (20) for females, at a rate of (9%). Most of the researchers were of Yemeni nationality with (222) theses at a rate of (99%), with the scarcity of students from other nationalities with (3) theses at a rate of (1%). 2) The thematic trends were distributed according to the research authority (the research place) to (28) authorities, which included most government and private sectors and organizations, where the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in all its institutions obtained (31) studies at a rate of (13.8%), and the Ministry of Finance in all its sectors, departments and bodies came in second place with (25) studies at a rate of (11.1%). The Ministry of Planning, the Ministry of Fisheries, and the Ministry of Labor ranked last with one study for each ministry (0.40%). 3) While the theses were distributed according to the research fields to (17) main areas, where the field of trends and administrative entries ranked first by (34) repetitions, and by (15.10%), and each of the areas of organizational effectiveness and human resources management ranked second by (30) repetitions, and by (13.30%), while the field of organizational culture, gender and women's issues ranked last by two repetitions, and by (0.90%). In light of the results of the research, several recommendations and suggestions were made.

Keywords: Research Outputs, Scientific Publishing, Research Centers, Administrative Development, Republic of Yemen.

1. THE GENERAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

1.1. Introduction:

The building of modern society requires us to pay attention to the knowledge and research structure, and attention to higher education is one of the keys to the wheel of construction and development throughout the world, as scientific research represents the basic basis from which economic, political and social development projects are launched, and it also represents one of the most important aspects of the progress of countries, and the clear disparity between developed and developing countries is mainly due to investment in scientific research and the application of its results in all development sectors, and the accelerated development in developed countries depends on the outputs of the educational and academic process, starting mainly from universities and scientific research centers.

Hence, universities, higher education institutions, and scientific and research centers had their main role in pushing forward the wheel of comprehensive development, by focusing on the capacities, energies, and qualified and trained human resources capable of leading the development process and developing them in those universities, institutions, and scientific and research centers. Therefore, it became necessary for developing countries to take the initiative to develop their universities, institutions and scientific and research centers to enable them to perform this role efficiently and effectively [1].

The establishment of the Public Administration Development Center at Sana'a University in 2007 represented a qualitative addition in the field of higher education, in order to contribute to building administrative leaders capable of bearing the burdens of advancing the development wheel in Yemen. This center was established as a result of cooperation between our country and donors, as it was established within a new mechanism that ensures work and achievement in light of the best financial, administrative, and academic practices and methods in force in universities and prestigious centers in the world. To this end, the Dutch side, represented by the Institute of Public Administration (ROI) and the University of Leiden, participated in the preparation and approval process of all the financial, administrative, and academic components of the center, which lasted for more than four years, based on the best international standards, specifically the standards approved by the European Union.

The establishment of the center was in line with the government's directions in the process of financial and administrative reform, and with the increase in the number of students applying for the center, which reached (751) students during the period from (2007) to the end of (2020), and the number of students who completed the study of the subjects (371) students, and the writing of the research was completed by only (225) students.

The scientific research accomplished at the Center for the Development of Public Administration is a valuable knowledge asset. The number of (225) researchers is not insignificant. There is no doubt that these researches have taken different paths and directions. The analysis and study of the trends of these studies and scientific research and the extent of their contribution to the process of administrative development are important topics that the Center is required to achieve to advance development in Yemen, especially in light of the increasing number of scientific theses in public administration. There is a clear scarcity in the studies related to their evaluation and analysis of their trends and research topics. Since the opening of the Center's graduate program, the objective trends of the scientific theses have not been identified at the Center, and previous local studies have not addressed this topic. Therefore, it is clear that there is an urgent need to conduct a study to analyze the contribution of the scientific theses at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University in administrative development, which is the goal of the current research.

1.2. The Problem of the Study:

The importance of the problem lies in the importance of the leading role that the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University requires it to play as one of the scientific and research centers at the university. Its main task is to contribute to raising and modernizing public administration in Yemen to achieve official and popular ambitions in the fields of development and building the state of law and

order, as well as to advance the role of Sana'a University as a leading scientific institution in the national efforts to develop and develop government agencies and public institutions, and to provide consultations and implement research, studies and programs aimed at raising the level of performance of public administration in Yemen [2].

This research comes as an attempt to monitor and analyze the research submitted by master's students, approved by the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University for the period (2007-2020), and subject it to analysis according to many variables, and from the above, and based on a review of the literature and previous studies related to the subject, the research problem can be formulated in the following two questions:

- 1) What is the reality of scientific theses at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University according to variables: gender, nationality, and research entity (place of research)?
- 2) What is the analysis of the thesis trends at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University according to its research topics?

1.3. The Objectives of the Study:

- 1) Diagnosing the reality of scientific theses at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University according to the variables: gender, nationality, and research entity (place of research).
- 2) Analyzing the trends of theses at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University according to its research topics.

1.4. The Significance of the Study:

The Significance of research is highlighted in several aspects:

- The importance of research stems from the fact that it falls within the field of studies concerned with research and analysis of the role of one of the scientific and research centers, and therefore the research is considered an entry point for understanding the educational system in it.
- It may help state decision-makers and researchers to identify the topics that have been researched in the field of public administration and to benefit from them in practice to bridge between the practical and theoretical framework.
- This research comes to monitor and analyze the role of the Center for the Development of Public Administration in the development process through the interest of scientific research, and therefore the subject of research is an introduction to understanding some aspects of the educational system in the state on the one hand and reveal the dilemmas facing it on the other hand.

1.5. Limitation of the Study:

The research was limited to analyzing the theses submitted by postgraduate students at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University, which was licensed in the field of public administration for the period (2007-2020).

1.6. Terms of the Study:

Research Centers: They are a gathering and organization of a distinguished and specialized elite of researchers who are engaged in an in-depth and extensive study to provide future consultations or scenarios that can help decision-makers modify or draw up their policy based on these proposals in different fields [3].

The researchers define research centers procedurally as those centers that conduct scientific research based on the needs of society, whether on their initiative to develop solutions to a problem that a particular party suffers from or at the request of a particular party.

Scientific Research: It is the set of organized efforts made by man using the scientific method and scientific rules to increase his control over his environment and discover and determine the relationships between its phenomena [4].

Procedurally: it is defined as a research process that follows scientific methods and methods to study the problems faced by public or private institutions or society and to find appropriate scientific solutions to them.

The Center for the Development of Public Administration: It is "a graduate program: master's, specialized certificates, training, consulting, and research." It was established in 2007 [2].

Procedural Definition: Researchers mean the Center for the Development of Public Administration. The Center, which was established by the decision of the President of the University No. (71) of 2006, and enjoys legal personality and independent financial disclosure, and aims to qualify administrative leaders in government agencies and public institutions, and to carry out research and studies and provide consultations, in various aspects of management.

1.7. Previous Studies:

Given the importance of previous studies in determining the course of this research, achieving integration in the effort exerted and building on it, and bridging the knowledge gap, the researchers referred to several studies, and previous studies were classified as follows:

The study [5] entitled "The Role of Research Centers in Solving the Problems of Contemporary Society". The research aimed to identify the role of research centers in addressing the problems of contemporary societies and used the survey approach to achieve the objectives of the research. The research reached several results, the most prominent of which is that the number of research in the research centers concerned is small, if compared to the objectives of their establishment. That local community institutions do not present their problems and issues to research centers, and that researchers, by competence and experience, research problems, issues, and phenomena that approach the interests of the research centers to which they belong.

The study [6] entitled "Analysis of Objective Trends of Scientific Theses in the Department of Educational Management and Planning at Sana'a University for the period (1997-2019)". The research aimed to analyze the objective trends of the theses approved by the Department of Educational Management and Planning. To achieve the goal of the research, the descriptive-analytical and documentary approach was used. The research reached some results, the most prominent of which are: that the master's theses are double doctoral theses, the number of general education theses

was double their number in higher education, and the omission of scientific theses for two areas of research, namely: the field of scientific and educational media and the marketing of educational services, and the field of authorship, translation and publication.

1.7.1 Aspects of Benefiting from Previous Studies:

- Directing researchers to some sources and references through reference lists for these studies.
- Review the methodology used in previous studies and data and information collection tools.

1.7.2 What Distinguishes the Current Research from Previous Studies:

- This research is distinguished by the fact that it was conducted at a vital educational center in Yemeni society, which is the center for the development of public administration for the rehabilitation of state leaders and the development of public administration in Yemen, as well as the first research to analyze the research provided by the center.

2. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

2.1. The Establishment and Development of Studies and Research Centers:

Emerging in the post-World War I era, think tanks served as platforms for collective discussion, or for the study of administrative and social issues that preoccupy society or decision-makers.

The first research centers were established in the 20th and 30th eras, and they were the first research centers in the United States of America, through the founding of the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace in 1910, the Brookings Institution in 1916, the Hoover Institution in 1918, the 1919 Century Foundation, the Council on Foreign Relations in 1921, the National Bureau of Economics Research in 1920, and other research centers.

In Britain, the Royal Institute of International Affairs was established in 1920, in France, the French Institute of International Relations was established, and in Germany, the German Academy of Peace was established in 1931. It is noted in this era that most of these centers could not directly affect public policymakers, and were seen as academic institutions far from influencing national or international policies, although their impact indirectly through the formulation of public opinion positions rather than the process of influencing policymakers. In the post-Cold War era, their research interests evolved towards focusing on pivotal and complex issues, and research centers, studies, and opinion polls center in democratic countries have a clear influence and influence in influencing decision-makers and formulating public policies, both at the national level and the foreign policies of countries [7].

2.1.1. The Role and Importance of Research and Studies Centers in Decision-Making and Public Policy-Making:

Research and studies centers in most countries of the world in general, and America and Europe in particular, have become an essential role in the production of knowledge and scientific research and the resulting applications at the level of directing and formulating the public policy of countries in their various economic,

social, political, educational and other fields, in addition to rationalizing the decision, and in many cases, the decision is taken by officials and decision-makers in certain issues as determined by the results of research center studies. Research centers in America and much of the developed world have become a fixed part of the political structure and an organic part of the policy-making process in those countries [8].

The study [9] indicates that in modern societies or developed countries, there is a clear correlation between the development process and scientific and applied research, including opinion polls and field research, and that this correlation is necessary in the case of developing countries as well, for a set of objectives, including:

- 1) Reveal the development priorities in the community, and what are the easiest and fastest ways to achieve them through the use of local resources.
- 2) Developing local scientific research in line with the needs of the local environment and employing self-resources.
- 3) Support decision-making and make it more rational.

2.1.2. The Role of Study and Research Centers in the Arab World:

At the Arab level, [10] stated that the role of studies and research centers in the Arab world intersects in parts with some of the recognized roles of research centers in the Western world, but the role of Arab research centers is in a state of development and growth, both in terms of spread and in terms of impact and effectiveness, but the matter is still in undeveloped stages. On the other hand, Arab research centers tend to be associated either with the government sector or with Arab universities. As for research centers related to the private sector, their role and mobility have emerged relatively recently, although their most important roles are as follows:

- 1) Scientific publishing, whether on hot issues or issues of interest to the Arab public.
- 2) The organization of scientific activities such as conferences and workshops is often in political issues and areas or international changes that fall within the interest of official decision-makers, and thus the necessary funding is provided by certain ministries or government sectors or decision-makers in the state.
- 3) Preparing special advisory studies as mandated by decision-makers on public or sensitive issues.
- 4) Follow up on developments in global trends and the affairs of the region or provide summaries of these developments to decision-makers.
- 5) Work to study and conduct local public opinion surveys on issues or decisions before or after their issuance, or work to identify the needs and requirements of the people. These surveys are often subject to private information and not publication.

2.1.3. The Importance and Role of Research Centers in the Development of Knowledge:

The importance of research centers is because many of the problems of the contemporary world, which the bulk of their solution is not within the responsibility of the general public or their executive elites, but rather within the responsibility of elite institutions with a high knowledge focus, to determine the nature of the problems, ways to solve them, and move with a clear vision towards the future while overcoming

obstacles and overcoming challenges. Research and studies centers come to the forefront of these institutions.

What distinguishes these centers from others is their leading role in building countries and societies, the urgent need for them with the complexity of thought and knowledge issues, and the multiplicity of information sources in a world that is heading towards greater convergence in light of the growing globalization movement and the progress of technology. (James McGinn), one of the experts at the Policy Research Institute in the United States talks about the importance of research centers. He says: They are not only used to provide information but they are used to develop and decide the policy agenda, that is, they are carried out through their studies and research in political decision-making [11].

2.1.4. Rankings of Research Centers:

There are several classifications of research centers according to several criteria, as follows [12]:

- 1) **In terms of funding:** Research centers are divided in terms of funding into government research centers, academic research centers, whether they are affiliated with universities or rely on academics in their work, and private research centers, whether they are associated with providing public benefit or providing benefit to the parties that established them, such as companies, for example, and these are many and varied.
- 2) **In terms of political or ideological orientation:** It is divided into liberal research centers, conservative research centers: religious, national, social, leftist research centers, and intellectually independent research centers.
- 3) **In terms of independence:** examples include independent research centers, semi-independent research centers, university research centers, and partisan research centers.
- 4) **In terms of government linkage:** It is divided into: government research centers, that is, administratively and financially linked to governments. parastatal research centers, i.e. administratively independent of governments. Private research centers, which are independent of governments administratively and financially, rely on themselves to manage their affairs.
- 5) **In terms of specialization:** There are centers specialized in a specific field of knowledge.
- 6) **In terms of geographical scope:** It is divided into centers concerned with a specific geographical area such as a country or a continent.

2.2. The Establishment and Development of the "Center for the Development of Public Administration" in Yemen:

The continuous development in developed countries depends on the outputs of educational institutions represented in universities and scientific research centers. In this sense, the establishment of the center was in line with the directions of the government, especially in the areas of preparing and qualifying administrative leaders entrusted with achieving popular and official ambitions in the field of administrative development and achieving comprehensive and sustainable development goals.

To meet the challenges and transformations witnessed by the Yemeni reality at the level of public administration, an agreement was signed between the Yemeni government represented by the University of Sana'a, the Dutch government represented by the Institute of Public Administration (ROI), and the University of Leiden, stipulating the establishment of an executive master's program in public administration to prepare and qualify administrative leaders in government agencies, public institutions, and civil society organizations. The Center was established by the President of the University No. (71) of 2006 and the internal regulations of the Center were issued by the President of the University No. (72) of 2007.

2.2.1. The Center Aims:

- 1) Training and qualifying administrative leaders in government agencies and public institutions, by providing them with the administrative (theoretical) knowledge and the specialized (applied) skills required to improve their performance, with a focus on the latest knowledge and successful administrative experience in brotherly and friendly countries.
- 2) Carrying out research and studies and providing consultations in various aspects of management required by government agencies and public institutions.
- 3) Holding seminars, workshops, and conferences aimed at discussing various shortcomings and imbalances in the public administration system, and working to develop the necessary methodological and scientific solutions and treatments.
- 4) Working to create a stimulating, fruitful, and sustainable academic climate for faculty members active in various fields, which is required by the process of raising the level of performance of public administration in Yemen.
- 5) Coordinate with local and foreign institutions interested in various aspects of the development and reform of public administration in Yemen.
- 6) Working on twinning the center with the relevant centers, institutes, and universities.
- 7) Seeking academic accreditation locally and abroad.
- 8) Participate in internal and external conferences and seminars.

2.2.2. Preparations for the Establishment of the Center:

To establish a center that represents a qualitative addition to the educational programs at Sana'a University and the higher education system in general, those in charge of establishing the Public Administration Development Center from the Dutch and Yemeni sides, under the supervision of the university leadership and the Ministry of Higher Education, worked to implement some events, the most prominent of which was the holding of the Public Administration Conference in Yemen, whose objectives were determined as follows:

- Bringing together all the target parties of the program with their different goals, needs, methods, and work locations, to identify common ground, concepts, and perceptions to determine the objectives of the program and the quality of the materials to be provided through it.

- Identify the role of public administration in Yemen, the challenges it may face now and in the future, and the institutional arrangements required by the university to meet those challenges.
- Agreeing on the requirements for improving performance in the public service, ways and mechanisms to achieve them in light of modern methods in public administration, and the role of the Center in enhancing the role of the public office in the development of society and raising the level of performance of administrative leaders.
- Determine the type of capabilities and skills needed by those in charge of the financial and administrative reform process, which the center can provide through training rehabilitation, and research and consultancy.

2.2.3. Information on the Study Programme at the Center:

- 1) The program is a scientific and practical addition to the field of public administration in the Republic of Yemen, as it is the only one concerned with qualifying leaders in the administrative apparatus of the state and civil society organizations.
- 2) The program contributes to reshaping the administrative culture of the leaders in the administrative apparatus of the state and civil society organizations.
- 3) Highlighting the importance of practical, methodological, and technical orientation within the administrative apparatus of the state and civil society organizations, and its reflection on the level of performance of these agencies and institutions.
- 4) Allowing leaders in the administrative apparatus of the state and civil society organizations to continue their higher education locally.
- 5) The leaders in the administrative apparatus of the state and civil society organizations were briefed on the latest developments in the world of administration and public policy globally, and how to reduce the gap between global performance and the performance of public administration in our country.

2.2.4. Beneficiaries of the Program:

The beneficiaries of the program are the following:

- Ministries, local authority bodies, and public and mixed institutions.
- Civil society organizations and private sector institutions.
- International organizations working in Yemen and accredited Arab embassies in Yemen.

2.2.5. Executive Master's Program:

The Executive Master's Program in Public Administration is dedicated to administrative leaders in government and private agencies and civil society organizations and seeks to achieve the following objectives:

2.2.6. The Program Aims [13]:

- 1) Providing administrative leaders with an in-depth understanding of management and public policy locally, regionally, and globally.
- 2) Upgrading the capabilities of administrative leaders and providing them with the necessary knowledge and techniques to face developments in the field of government work.
- 3) Encouraging and supporting applied research in the fields of administration and public policy, foremost of which is administrative development, organizational development, and public policy analysis.
- 4) Paying attention to contemporary management and public policy issues, and the problems facing society and government in Yemen.
- 5) Building bridges of trust with government agencies and civil society organizations to learn more about the quality and nature of the challenges facing them, and working to provide the necessary solutions to meet those challenges.
- 6) Providing management leaders with managerial and analytical skills that enable them to deal positively with these challenges.
- 7) Focus on instilling positive values, ethics, and desired behaviors in the public service, in light of the challenges facing public administration in Yemen, and ensure that administrative leaders understand and understand the exceptional and distinctive nature of government work at the current stage and in the future.

2.2.7. The Role of the Center in the Development of Public Administration in Yemen:

The establishment of the center is a scientific and practical addition to the level of university education, as it is the academic institutional entity concerned with the areas of administrative development, foremost of which is the qualification of leaders in the administrative apparatus of the state. Within a short period, the Center was able to attract a group of administrative leaders in government agencies, including ministers, governors, agents, and heads of public and mixed institutions and bodies [14].

The Center was also able to prepare applied research (whether in the reports required from administrative leaders within the curricula or in graduation research), and it may address fundamental aspects at the level of administrative development that, if approved by the competent authorities in the government, would modernize public administration, develop organizational effectiveness in the administrative apparatus of the state, and develop the processes of making, implementing and evaluating public policy in Yemen.

The Center has also contributed to making fundamental changes in the organizational culture and leadership and management behaviors of the Center's students, which were manifested in the adoption by these leaders of strategic planning and management methods in the agencies and institutions in which they work. The Center's experience has shown in record time the possibility of breaking the barrier that used to prevent the process of fruitful communication between administrative leaders and public policy-makers on the one hand and academics and academic institutions on the other [15].

The Center has an important role in activating the role of the university in meeting the increasing needs of society and government, especially in the fields of scientific and practical research, consultancy, and rehabilitation, which were imposed by the challenges of building the modern Yemeni state and achieving the goals of comprehensive and sustainable development.

3. THE PRACTICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

3.1. Research Methodology:

The current research relied on the descriptive-analytical and documentary approach, where the necessary information and data were collected from the research submitted by graduate students at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University, a method that aims to study the objective directions of those theses.

3.2. Research Community:

The research community consists of all the research submitted by graduate students to obtain a master's degree, which was approved by the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University, for the period: (2007-2020), and the bibliographic data was obtained for those research, which are (225) scientific theses, and the tool was applied to all scientific theses, due to the lack of the research community.

3.3. Research Tool:

A form has been designed to collect information from scientific research at the Center by the following steps:

- Reviewing the scientific literature related to the research topic to identify the research tools in which it was used to collect information, and how to identify research areas. Since there is no unified classification of the fields and topics of public administration, the current research relied on reviewing the description of postgraduate courses in the specialization of public administration.
- Preparation of a form consisting of two parts; the first part contains: information on the research variables, including gender, nationality, and place of research. The second part contains the areas of public administration, which were identified by the researchers. For the current research and the construction of the tool, the research community was distributed into units called research areas. The research concluded by identifying (17) main areas under which all research topics in public administration, called units of analysis, can fall.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Answer to the first question:

What is the reality of the theses of the Center for the Development of Public Administration at the University of Sana'a according to variables: gender, nationality, research entity (place of research)?

To answer this question, the data were collected using the form that was built for this purpose, through which the required information was provided about (225) scientific theses, and then calculating their frequency, analysis, and interpretation. The following are the results of analyzing the scientific theses of the students of the Center for the

Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University, according to some variables, as follows:

- **Type variable:**

It means the number of research carried out by male researchers and the number of research carried out by female researchers.

Table No. (1): Distribution of theses according to the gender variable

No	Gender	Number	Percentage
1	Male	205	91%
2	Female	20	9%
	Total	225	100%

It is clear from the above table that the number of male researchers reached (205) and (91%) of the total sample, while the number of female researchers reached (20) and (9%) of the total sample, which indicates the increase in the number of male researchers compared to the number of females, as a result of the impact of the Yemeni environment on the recruitment process of workers, and that most of the leaders in the country are males, which was directly reflected in the number of those leaders enrolled in the center.

- **Nationality variable:**

It means the number of researches carried out by Yemeni researchers, and of other nationalities.

Table No. (2): Distribution of scientific theses according to the nationality variable

No	Nationality of researchers	Number	Percentage
1	Yemeni	222	99%
2	Non-Yemeni	3	1%
	Total	225	100%

It is clear from the above table that the number of Yemeni researchers reached (222) and (99%) of the total sample, while the number of non-Yemeni researchers reached (3) and (1%) of the total sample, represented by researchers from the State of Iraq and a researcher from the Sultanate of Oman, and this is a natural result where the center was established to qualify Yemeni administrative leaders while opening the way for non-Yemenis to qualify.

- **Research entity variable (research location):**

It means the place where the research is carried out.

Table No. (3): Distribution of scientific theses according to the research authority (place of research)

No	Research Entities	frequencies	Percentage	Order
1.	Ministry of Higher Education	31	13.80%	1
2.	Ministry of Finance	25	11.10%	2
3.	Presidency of the Republic	21	9.30%	3
4.	Ministry of Telecommunications	13	5.80%	4
5.	Ministry of Health	13	5.80%	4
6.	Ah, local law.	13	5.80%	4
7.	Missile program	11	4.90%	5
8.	Civil Service	10	4.40%	6

No	Research Entities	frequencies	Percentage	Order
9.	International and local organizations	9	4.00 %	7
10.	Ministry of the Interior	9	4.00 %	7
11.	Other	9	4.00 %	7
12.	Private sector	8	3.60%	8
13.	Office of the Prime Minister	8	3.60%	8
14.	Ministry of Education	6	2.70 %	9
15.	Ministry Of Agriculture	6	2.70 %	9
16.	Ministry of Lands, Mines and Energy	5	2.20%	10
17.	Ministry of Electricity + Ministry of Water	5	2.20%	10
18.	Ministry of Technical Education	3	1.30%	11
19.	Ministry of Youth and Sports	3	1.30%	11
20.	The House of Representatives and the Shura Council	3	1.30%	11
21.	Ministry of Justice + Judicial Council	3	1.30 %	11
22.	Ministry of Local Administration	2	0.90 %	12
23.	Ministry of Defense	2	0.90 %	12
24.	Ministry of Expatriates Affairs	2	0.90 %	12
25.	Ministry of Culture + Ministry of Information	2	0.90 %	12
26.	Ministry of Planning	1	0.40 %	13
27.	Ministry of Fishery Resources	1	0.40 %	13
28.	Ministry of Labour	1	0.40 %	13
Total		225	100%	

It is clear from the above table that the number of researches that were written in more than (28) entities included all government and private sectors and organizations. The researchers attribute these results to the keenness of the leadership of the center to qualify all sectors and achieve the goals for which the center was established, including, but not limited to, the second goal, which reads "*Conducting research and studies and providing consultations in various aspects of management required by government agencies and public institutions*".

As can be seen from the above table, the highest authority in which studies and research were carried out was the Ministry of Higher Education in all its institutions, where it reached (31) studies at a rate of (13.8%), which is the highest in which research was carried out. The researchers attribute these results to the environment of the center, which is one of the centers affiliated with Sana'a University, as well as the interest of the leadership of the Ministry of Higher Education in qualifying its leadership, while the Ministry of Finance came in second place with (25) studies at a rate of (11.1%), while the Presidency of the Republic came in third place with (21) studies at a rate of (9.3%). The share of international and local organizations in studies and research was (9) studies at a rate of (4.0%), while the share of the private sector was (8) studies at a rate of (3.6%). The researchers attribute these results to the fact that the center was established to qualify state leaders directly, but the center was keen to contribute to raising and modernizing public administration in Yemen in general and to achieving official and popular ambitions in the fields of development. International and local organizations and the private sector were targeted through (17) diverse studies in terms of their topics and fields, while the Ministry of Planning, the Ministry of Fisheries, the Ministry of Information, the Ministry of Culture, and the Ministry of Labor ranked in the best position with only one study for each entity at a rate of (0.4%).

Answer to the second question:

What is the analysis of the thesis trends at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University according to its research topics?

To answer the question, the number of repetitions of master's theses that were approved at the center was calculated, after the researchers prepared a list of research titles for graduate students at the center, and then linked those titles to the previously identified fields, which amounted to (17) main areas under which all research topics in public administration can fall, and Table No. (4) shows this.

Table No. (4): Distribution of scientific theses according to the research fields.

No	Research Areas	frequencies	Percentage	Order
1.	Trends and administrative entrances	34	15.10%	1
2.	Organizational effectiveness	30	13.30%	2
3.	Human Resources Department	30	13.30%	2
4.	Performance Development + Development	23	10.20 %	3
5.	Administrative reform	18	8.00 %	4
6.	Quality	18	8.00 %	4
7.	Information Systems	16	7.10 %	5
8.	Leadership and Governance 6	11	4.89 %	6
9.	Financial Management	9	4.00 %	7
10.	Strategic Planning + Strategies	9	4.00 %	7
11.	policies	8	3.56 %	8
12.	Knowledge Department	6	2.70 %	9
13.	Performance evaluation	3	1.30 %	10
14.	Censorship	3	1.30 %	10
15.	Crisis Management	3	1.30 %	10
16.	Organizational culture	2	0.90 %	11
17.	Gender and women's issues	2	0.90 %	11
Total		225	100%	

It is clear from the previous table that the field of (trends and administrative entries) ranked first among (17) research fields, with 34 repetitions and (15.10%). This is because most of the graduate students of the Public Administration Program at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University are those who occupy leadership and administrative positions in all state institutions, which are shown in Table (3). Most of them exercise the functions of public administration in practice and seek to develop their performance by applying what has been studied in practice. They include undersecretaries, consultants, general managers, and department managers. Therefore, they can sense administrative problems, based on the nature of their work, which makes it easier for them to choose research problems in the field of administrative trends and entrances. Researchers usually tend to new topics and recent trends, including: "Empowerment, delegation, and management of results and objectives, and the application of codification and the pursuit of competitive advantage in their institutions". On the other hand, the field of administrative trends and entrances is a wide and exciting area for research questions, and advocacy for continuous research and study.

While the field of (organizational effectiveness) ranked second with (30) repetitions and by (13.30%), this is due to the keenness of most researchers to know the reality of the entities in which they work through the analysis of organizational effectiveness by applying the Cotter model, and came in second place repeating the field of (human resources management) with (30) repetitions and by (13.30%), This is due to the

conviction of researchers in this field that the essential element in the progress of management and bringing about radical change in it is the study and analysis of topics and trends of human resources management in all its modern directions, to know the defects and develop solutions and recommendations that contribute to solving them. The three previous areas were the most studied and researched by graduate students in the Public Administration Program at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University.

Through the above results, it is clear that the areas of greatest interest among postgraduate students at the Center were: administrative trends and entries, organizational effectiveness, human resources management, performance development and development, and administrative reform, and then the researcher paid attention to the topics of modern administration and its entrances, such as quality, strategic planning, crisis management, policy-making, and knowledge management, and then the rest of the trends and modern administrative entrances. The researchers attribute this to the interest of supervising professors and researchers in modern administrative trends and entrances in their various dimensions, to try to apply them to practical reality, to consolidate the distinguished institutional performance in the state administrative apparatus and civil society organizations, based on good governance, and making it a sustainable administrative approach to achieve high levels of performance.

5. CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1. Conclusions:

In light of the results of the previous theoretical literature, and the results of the analysis of the current research, the following was drawn:

- There are good and tangible achievements in the field of graduate studies and scientific research at Sana'a University, in terms of expanding the number of programs and the percentage of enrollment in them, but there is a clear deficiency in the absence of research plans and strategies at the level of scientific departments, colleges, research and scientific centers, and at the university level.
- The number of male researchers is still large compared to the number of females, which indicates that there are few opportunities for females and that there is a need to create more opportunities for females to continue postgraduate studies like males.
- Weak security and instability in the country, and the absence of a marketing and promotion policy for Yemeni university services, are among the most prominent reasons that led to the low number of international students at Sana'a University.
- Most of the objective trends of graduate students are concentrated in the field of modern administrative trends and approaches, the field of organizational effectiveness, the field of leadership and governance, the organizational culture, institutional structures and the work environment, and finally gender studies and women's issues.
- There are still research areas and administrative sectors that need to carry out research and studies that contribute to the development of the administrative process, such as electronic management, the educated organization, strategic

planning, the development of institutional capacity and competitive advantage, and others.

- The process of selecting graduate students for their research topics is carried out in a personal manner, and there is no research map at the Center for the Development of Public Administration or a specific mechanism to organize the process of selecting research topics.
- Neglecting to draw the attention of graduate students to the most important issues and problems facing the public administration in the societal reality leads to the inactivity of scientific research in developing appropriate solutions and proposals by identifying research areas for them according to the needs of society, and linking them to different educational institutions.

5.2. Recommendations:

The research reached some recommendations, the most prominent of which are the following:

- Developing educational policy, and evaluation methods, and avoiding repetition and duplication of research topics, so that such research integrates and forms an extension of each other and is comprehensive of all administrative problems and issues.
- Developing the vision and mission of the Public Administration Development Center, to achieve integration, diversity, and interdependence between the fields of scientific research, and paying attention to all administrative issues and problems without neglecting each other.
- Paying attention to evaluative studies on an ongoing basis and using various research methods.
- Studying the trends and research topics of scientific theses every five years to evaluate and develop them.
- Defining clear, specific, and declared criteria for the selection of research fields and topics, taking into account the priority of research, so that it is characterized by excellence, modernity, originality, and innovation, without repeating what has already been studied.
- Developing the content of scientific research curricula, and encouraging students to participate in scientific meetings held inside the country to benefit from the available scientific ideas and visions.
- Developing units for marketing university services and research projects and introducing them.
- Addressing new research areas, such as the development of institutional capacity, the competitive advantage of government institutions, and administrative excellence, as well as studying the mechanisms of transition towards e-government and the application of good governance standards, and others.
- Organizing conferences, meetings, and workshops for new researchers to introduce them to research areas, and building a bibliographic database, guides, and guides to the scientific theses of the Center for the Development of Public Administration.

- Activating the role of Sana'a University House for printing and publishing, and facilitating the printing of distinguished scientific theses, which obtained recommendations for printing at the university's expense, and publishing them in paper and electronic form.
- Benefiting from the results of this research in developing a research plan for the Center for the Development of Public Administration, so that it relies on a balanced scientific vision that contributes to determining the future directions of administrative research, and includes the various research fields mentioned in the study and others, and directing students towards them.
- Creating an institutional entity that includes holders of higher qualifications from the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University since the establishment of the center until the preparation of the study, to strengthen relations between them and their peers in similar universities, to exchange knowledge and research experiences, to disseminate scientific and research culture, exchange studies, conduct collective research, and implement seminars, workshops, panel discussions, and scientific conferences. It may require the establishment of a scientific association for public administration at the national level, and the issuance of a scientific journal affiliated to it.

5.3. Suggestions:

- Conducting a study to explore the future of public administration research at the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a University, in light of development priorities and the requirements of the twenty-first century.
- Conducting a study to analyze the methodology and knowledge content of the theses at the Public Administration Development Center.
- Conducting a scientific study to design a research map for the Center for the Development of Public Administration at Sana'a Private University, and another study to design a research map for the public administration of Yemeni universities as a whole.
- Conducting a comprehensive study to find out the research topics required in the public administration by all beneficiaries: in the government and private sectors, researchers, the university's postgraduate department, the scientific research sector of the Ministry of Higher Education, research centers, supporting organizations, and relevant authorities.

References

- 1) Al-Khatib, Ahmed (2001) University Administration - Recent Studies, Hamada Foundation for University Studies, Publishing and Distribution, Jordan.
- 2) The internal regulations of the Center issued by the decision of the President of the University No. (72) of 2007.
- 3) Zaidan, Essam: Research centers ambitious goals and missing links, an article published on the International Internet of Information www.siironline.org
- 4) Adas Abdul Rahman, et al. (1989), Scientific Research, its Concept, Tools and Methods, Nael Publishing House, Amman.

- 5) Al-Jumaili, Azim (2016) The Role of Research Centers in Solving the Problems of Contemporary Society, Journal of the Babylon Center for Humanities Studies, Special Edition of the National Conference of Sciences and Letters, Volume 6/p 4.
- 6) Al-Khatib, Khalil & Al-Hamdani Raja (2020), Analysis of Thematic Trends of Scientific Theses in the Department of Educational Management and Planning at Sana'a University for the period (1997-2019), Journal of Queen Arwa University Yemen, p. 24.
- 7) Robert O 'Neill, "Think Tanks & Their Impact", *Asia-Pacific Review*, Vol. 15 No. 2, pp9-12, 2008.
- 8) Ahmad, Mahmood. "US Think Tanks and the Politics of Expertise: Role, Value and Impact", *The Political Quarterly*, Vol. 79, No. 4, October-December, 2008.
- 9) Al-Fares, Abdul Razzaq Fares (2003), Research and Decision-Making Centers in the United Arab Emirates, Journal of Economic Development and Policy, Volume V, Second Issue, June.
- 10) Shehadeh, Mahdi & Al-Tayyar, Saleh (1999), The Role of Arab Studies Centers in Decision-Making, Beirut: Center for Arab-European Studies.
- 11) Awad, Saeed (2006), Obstacles and Problems of Administrative and Environmental Scientific Research in Yemeni Universities from the Point of View of a Faculty Member, Research of the Scientific Research Conference in the Arab World and Problems of Publishing, Arab Organization for Administrative Development, Egypt.
- 12) Mahmoud, Khaled (2003), Research Centers in the Arab World, Conceptual Framework, Roles, Challenges and the Future, Namaa Center for Research and Studies Beirut.
- 13) Regulation of the Graduate Studies Program at the Center for the Development of Public Administration, issued by the President of the University Resolution No. (727) of 2007.
- 14) Guide to the Center for the Development of Public Administration, 2010.
- 15) Nasser, Ahmed (2014), Developing the Performance of the Center for the Development of Public Administration in Light of Quality Standards, Unpublished Master Thesis, Center for the Development of Public Administration, Sana'a University, Yemen.